

BENNIE: THE DEVELOPED VIDEO -ENRICHED SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS IN TRENDS, NETWORKS, AND CRITICAL THINKING IN THE 21st CENTURY FOR GRADE 12 SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

This research aimed to develop and validate culturally relevant video-based supplementary materials for the subject Trends, Networks, and Critical Thinking in the 21st Century. It employed a quantitative research approach specifically utilizing a design and development study through pretest and posttest. Data were collected from thirty-five Grade 12-HUMMS in the University of Perpetual Help System DALTA – Calamba Campus and fifteen Social Studies and ICT teachers in both public and private schools using a purposive sampling technique. The study utilized an adopted and modified version of ready-made questionnaires with a content validity index of 1.00. A Paired Sample T-test was used to determine the significant difference between the pretest and posttest, while the mean and Likert Scale were used to identify the validity and acceptability of the supplementary materials. Moreover, it was revealed that the validity level of the supplementary materials was Very High in terms of objectives (\bar{x} =3.77), directions (\bar{x} =3.65), topics (\bar{x} =3.72), practical exercises (\bar{x} =3.57), and clarity (\bar{x} =3.73). In addition, the acceptability level of the video-enriched supplementary materials was Very Acceptable in terms of usefulness (\bar{x} =3.73), presentation (\bar{x} =3.80), and suitability (\bar{x} =3.67). Furthermore, it was revealed that the students did not meet expectations (\bar{x} =74.71) in the pretest, and the posttest result revealed Very Satisfactory with an average of 86.63. The results registered that there was a significant difference between the pretest and the posttest with a t value of -64.091 (SD=5.79, \bar{x} =-27.12). Therefore, the developed video-enriched supplementary materials were proposed to enhance students' ability to provide engaging and interactive learning

experiences that help students formulate a stance on contemporary issues and explore alternative futures.

Keywords: *BENNIE, Video-enriched Supplementary Materials, Trends, Networks, Critical Thinking*

INTRODUCTION

Globally, the use of video clips as supplemental materials has become a common practice, supported by studies such as Bebita (2022), which demonstrated their effectiveness in enhancing students' conceptual understanding and motivation. Video-based learning accommodated diverse learning styles by simplifying complex concepts through visual and auditory means. Similarly, Lowenthal et al. (2020) found out that short videos promote an engaging learning environment and support the development of higher-order thinking skills essential in addressing 21st-century challenges. This stunning fact highlighted the importance of education in preparing students for an unpredictable, technologically driven future.

Beyond enhancing academic performance, video-based learning fostered critical thinking skills essential in navigating technology's evolving landscape. By presenting real-world scenarios, like diverse cultural perspectives, and practical applications, the video clips helped the students to have informed decisions and better understanding of the global trends. As technology, social networks, and global participation continued to shape society, learners had only to acquire knowledge but also develop the ability to apply it meaningfully.

Despite global advancements, the Philippine education system faces unique challenges that require context-specific solutions. Given the country's diverse socioeconomic and cultural landscape, instructional materials must be thoughtfully designed to meet the needs of Filipino learners. Video-based supplementary materials in *Trends, Networks, and Critical Thinking in the 21st Century* offer strong potential, especially in areas with limited access to quality educational resources. Through multimedia, educators can provide inclusive and engaging learning experiences that bridge resource gaps.

Moreover, developing and validating culturally relevant video clips was critical for ensuring both educational efficacy and contextual relevance. Filipino students, who came from various ethnic and linguistic origins, gained benefits from educational materials that represented their personal experiences. Lessons on global trends, for example, became more significant when they were related to local examples, such as the impact of social media on political discourse or the significance of global networks in the Philippines. This contextualization improved and enriched students' comprehension of global challenges in their daily lives.

This study was driven by the urgent need to enhance critical thinking skills among Filipino students through innovative and engaging instructional methods. Critical thinking enabled learners to analyze data, recognize patterns, and solve complex problems—skills often underdeveloped by traditional teaching approaches. Traditional teaching approaches often emphasized rote memorization and standardized assessments, which limited opportunities for Filipino students to develop critical thinking skills. These methods typically focused on delivering fixed content rather than encouraging analysis, evaluation, or problem-solving. Additionally, they often lacked real-world applications, making it difficult for students to connect theoretical knowledge to practical situations. Integrating video clips into instruction fostered a more dynamic learning environment by presenting real-life scenarios, diverse perspectives, and opportunities for active engagement, leading to deeper and more effective learning.

BENNIE stands for Bridging Educational Needs through Networks, Innovation, and Engagement. This study acted as a guiding principle for the creation of supplementary materials. It emphasized not only the academic goal of closing learning gaps (Bridging Educational Needs) but also the importance of aligning content with 21st-century learning contexts (Networks) and embracing creative approaches (Innovation) to make the learning process more interactive and student-centered (Engagement). The title "BENNIE" also lends an understanding and different identity to the subject, making it easier to promote, carry out, and recognize in the classroom.

This study aimed to develop and validate culturally relevant video-based supplementary materials for the subject Trends, Networks, and Critical Thinking in the 21st Century. Its goal was to enhance student understanding, improve critical thinking skills, and provide an engaging learning experience. By integrating global best practices and adapting them to the Filipino educational context, the study addressed the limitations of traditional materials in teaching complex, modern concepts. These video resources were designed to support diverse learning styles and promoted active, meaningful learning among students.

In the 21st century, where social networks and rapid technological advancements shape daily life, educational paradigms evolve to address these changes. This study takes on the challenge by developing culturally relevant, video-based supplementary materials tailored to Filipino learners, empowering them with the skills to navigate an interconnected and complex world.

Research Objectives

This study developed and validated a Video-Enriched Supplementary Materials in Trends, Networks, and Critical Thinking in the 21st Century for Grade 12 Senior High School Students. Specifically, it attained the following purposes:

1. Design a video-enriched supplementary materials in Trends, Networks, and Critical Thinking in the 21st Century for Grade 12 Senior High School Students based and aligned with the K to 12 Curriculum MELCs.

2. Establish the content validity and acceptability of the developed Trends, Networks, and Critical Thinking in the 21st Century for Grade 12 Senior High School Students.
3. Determine the pretest and posttest results of the Grade 12 student participants upon utilizing the developed video-enriched supplementary materials in Trends, Networks, and Critical Thinking in the 21st Century for Grade 12 Senior High School Students.

METHODOLOGY

The research utilized quantitative methods through a design and development study. It was quantitative in the sense that it emphasized accurate measurements and statistical analysis or analytical data gathered from the students through tests. This centered on gathering quantifiable data and using it to figure out a specific event. It identified the significant difference between the pretest and the posttest of the students. This research was conducted in the University of Perpetual Help System DALTA - Calamba Campus, located in Paciano Rizal, Calamba City, Laguna, one of the well-known universities in Calamba, which was established in 1996 and offered courses from kindergarten to college. Focused on the STEM, ABM, and HUMSS strands, the Senior High School Department (SHS) offered not only academics, but also molded young entrepreneurs with the mantra of “Character Building is Nation Building.” The population for this included Social Studies master teachers, head teachers, and even an assistant principal with a Social Studies major in grad school from selected public and private schools in the Division of Calamba City. To administer the pretest and posttest, 35 HUMSS students from the University of Perpetual System DALTA served as respondents, using the purposive sampling technique, as they were qualified individuals who were suited for this study since it was made especially for them, as it was their major subject.

The respondents of this study were Grade 12 HUMSS students from the University of Perpetual Help System DALTA - Calamba Campus. A total of 35 students responded to the survey. They were the chosen respondents since the study was specifically aimed at their major subject, and 15 Social Studies teachers from selected public and private schools validated the developed video-enriched materials in Trends, Networks, and Critical Thinking in the 21st Century. The pretest was first developed to ensure the effectiveness and relevance of the data collection instrument for this study. To achieve this, an adopted and modified version of a ready-made questionnaire, specifically the Social Skills Rating System (SSRS), was utilized as the primary tool for gathering data. This questionnaire was carefully adjusted to align with the Development and Validation of Video-Enriched Supplementary Materials in Trends, Networks, and Critical Thinking in the 21st Century, ensuring comprehensive data collection. To ensure the validity of the Development and Validation of Video-Enriched Supplementary Materials, a pretest validation was conducted. Social Studies and ICT teachers from selected public and private schools assessed the effectiveness and suitability of the materials, making necessary adjustments to refine their

quality. While the researcher utilized standardized survey questions, expert opinions from professionals in the field were sought to further enhance the validation process. Their feedback and recommendations significantly contributed to refining and polishing the questionnaire, ensuring its relevance to the study.

This research ensured careful adherence to ethical protocols in data collection, obtaining prior consent from all respondents, including Social Studies teachers, master and head teachers, students, and the School Principal of UPHSD. An orientation session was conducted to clarify the study's objectives to all involved. Respondents were informed that the test data collected would be used exclusively for research purposes, with strict compliance with the provisions of the Data Privacy Act of 2012.

RESULTS

Table 1.1.1

Content Validity Level of Video-enriched Supplementary Materials in Trends, Networks, and Critical Thinking in the 21st Century in terms of Objectives

Indicators	\bar{X}	VI
1. Relevant to the topics in 21 st Century	3.87	HV
2. Specific and clearly Stated	3.87	HV
3. Measurable, attainable. And result-oriented	3.80	HV
4. Well-planned, formulated, and organized	3.73	HV
5. Time bound	3.60	HV
General Assessment	3.77	HV
Standard Deviation	0.35	
Legend:	3.25-4.00 Highly Valid (HV)	2.50-3.24 Valid (V)
	1.75-2.49 Slightly Valid (SV)	1.00-1.74 Not Valid (NV)

Table 1.1.2

Content Validity Level of Video-enriched Supplementary Materials in Trends, Networks, and Critical Thinking in the 21st Century in terms of Directions

Indicators	\bar{X}	VI
1. Simple and clear	3.60	HV
2. Easy to follow	3.60	HV
3. Properly sequenced	3.73	HV
4. Can be done independently	3.67	HV
General Assessment	3.65	HV
Standard Deviation	0.41	
Legend:	3.25-4.00 Highly Valid (HV)	2.50-3.24 Valid (V)

1.75-2.49 Slightly Valid (SV)

1.00-1.74 Not Valid (NV)

Table 1.1.3

Content Validity Level of Video-enriched Supplementary Materials in Trends, Networks, and Critical Thinking in the 21st Century in terms of Topics

Indicators		\bar{X}	VI
1.	Are sequenced according to curriculum	3.67	HV
2.	Are logically presented	3.60	HV
3.	Address the learners' needs	3.73	HV
4.	Are equipped with background and concepts	3.80	HV
5.	Are easily understood by the learners	3.80	HV
General Assessment		3.72	HV
Standard Deviation		0.36	
Legend:	3.25-4.00 Highly Valid (HV)	2.50-3.24 Valid (V)	
	1.75-2.49 Slightly Valid (SV)	1.00-1.74 Not Valid (NV)	

Table 1.1.4

Content Validity Level of Video-enriched Supplementary Materials in Trends, Networks, and Critical Thinking in the 21st Century in terms of Practical Exercises

Indicators		\bar{X}	VI
1.	Inconsonance with the objectives	3.60	HV
2.	Appropriate to learners' abilities	3.60	HV
3.	Adequate to enhance learners' comprehension and reading skills	3.60	HV
4.	Sufficient to determine the mastery level of learners	3.53	HV
5.	Stimulate higher order thinking skills	3.53	HV
General Assessment		3.57	HV
Standard Deviation		0.41	
Legend:	3.25-4.00 Highly Valid (HV)	2.50-3.24 Valid (V)	
	1.75-2.49 Slightly Valid (SV)	1.00-1.74 Not Valid (NV)	

Table 1.1.5

Content Validity Level of Video-enriched Supplementary Materials in Trends, Networks, and Critical Thinking in the 21st Century in terms of Clarity

Indicators		\bar{X}	VI
1.	Information is clear and simple	3.73	HV
2.	Language use is clear and easy to understand	3.73	HV

3. The concepts for each activity are re-arranged logically and ensure that there is no duplication	3.80	HV
4. Information suits learners' interest.	3.67	HV
General Assessment	3.73	HV
Standard Deviation	0.37	
Legend:	3.25-4.00 Highly Valid (HV)	2.50-3.24 Valid (V)
	1.75-2.49 Slightly Valid (PV)	1.00-1.74 Not Valid (NV)

Table 1.2.1

Level of Acceptability of Video-enriched Supplementary Materials in Trends, Networks, and Critical Thinking in the 21st Century in terms of Usefulness

Indicators	\bar{X}	VI
1. The materials prepares the learners to think logically and critically	3.73	VA
2. The concepts in the material are simple and comprehensible	3.80	VA
3. the material helps the students master the topics at their own pace	3.80	VA
4. The material provides opportunity for the development	3.67	VA
5. The learning contents provide adequate information on the topics presented	3.73	VA
6. The material motivates learners to become actively involved in the learning activities	3.67	VA
7. The material stimulates the learners to intellectual activities which help them master the least learned competencies	3.73	VA
8. The activities seek to relate new concepts from previous learning	3.73	VA
General Assessment	3.73	VA
Standard Deviation	0.41	
Legend:	3.25-4.00 Very Acceptable (VA)	2.50-3.24 Acceptable(A)
	1.75-2.49 Slightly Acceptable (PA)	1.00-1.74 Not Acceptable (NA)

Table 1.2.2

Level of Acceptability of Video-enriched Supplementary Materials in Trends, Networks, and Critical Thinking in the 21st Century in terms of Presentation

Indicators	\bar{X}	VI
1. Topics are presented in logical and sequential order	3.87	VA
2. The direction is concise readable, and easy to follow	3.80	VA
3. the topics fit the learners' needs	3.80	VA
4. The presentation of each lesson is attractive and interesting	3.73	VA

General Assessment	3.80	VA
Standard Deviation	0.34	

Legend: 3.25-4.00 Very Acceptable (VA) 2.50-3.24 Acceptable(A)
1.75-2.49 Slightly Acceptable (SA) 1.00-1.74 Not Acceptable (NA)

Table 1.2.3

Level of Acceptability of Video-enriched Supplementary Materials in Trends, Networks, and Critical Thinking in the 21st Century in terms of Suitability

Indicators	X	VI
1. Activities consider the varying attitudes and capabilities	3.60	VA
2. Activities are appropriate to the subject matter	3.67	VA
3. Activities are relevant, interesting, and self-motivating to the learners	3.67	VA
4. Enrichment activities cater the different learning needs of learners	3.67	VA
5. Language of the program is within the vocabulary range of learners	3.73	VA
General Assessment	3.67	VA
Standard Deviation	0.43	

Legend: 3.25-4.00 Very Acceptable (VA) 2.50-3.24 Acceptable(A)
1.75-2.49 Slightly Acceptable (PA) 1.00-1.74 Not Acceptable (NA)

Table 2.1

Pretest Score of the Video-enriched Supplementary Materials in Trends, Networks, and Critical Thinking in the 21st Century

Indicators	Frequency	Percentage
Outstanding	0	0
Very Satisfactory	4	11.43
Satisfactory	5	14.29
Fairly Satisfactory	8	22.86
Did not meet Expectations	18	51.43
Total	35	100.00
Average	74.71	
Standard Deviation	7.21	

Legend: 90-100 Outstanding 85-89 Very Satisfactory 80-84 Satisfactory
75-79 Fairly Satisfactory 74 below Did not Meet Expectations

Table 2.2

Posttest Score of the Video-enriched Supplementary Materials in Trends, Networks, and Critical Thinking in the 21st Century

Indicators	Frequency	Percentage
Outstanding	16	45.71
Very Satisfactory	10	28.57
Satisfactory	4	11.43
Fairly Satisfactory	0	0
Did not meet Expectations	5	14.29
Total	35	100.00
Average	86.63	
Standard Deviation	7.82	

Legend: 90-100 Outstanding 85-89 Very Satisfactory 80-84 Satisfactory
75-79 Fairly Satisfactory 74 below Did not Meet Expectations

Table 2.3

Test of Significant Difference between the Pretest and Posttest Scores of Grade 12 Students

Indicators	Test	Paired Differences				Remarks	Decision
		Mean	SD	T	P value		
21 st century	Pre & Post	- 27.12	5.79	-64.091	.000	Significant	Reject Ho

DISCUSSION

This endeavor developed supplementary materials through video clips in Trends, Networks, and Critical Thinking in the 21st Century.

Research Objective Number 1. Design and develop supplementary materials through video clips in Trends, Networks, and Critical Thinking in the 21st Century.

As observed, a lack of enthusiasm among learners when engaging with the subject "Trends, Networks, and Critical Thinking in the 21st Century" became evident. This observation led to the development of supplementary materials in video clips, aiming to enhance student interest and engagement. The process followed a structured approach, consisting of four key phases: planning, designing and developing, validating and trying out, and, finally, evaluating and finishing.

During the planning phase, topics from the third quarter of the Academic Year 2024-2025 were carefully reviewed to ensure alignment with the K-12 curriculum guide. To ensure the quality and suitability of these supplemental materials, a few processes took place, that is why to make these materials possible, the script was generated using Chat GPT, the design, photos, and everything else in the film were done using Canva, and the video itself was created using PowToon. The supplementary materials were designed to address a wide range of learning capabilities, ensuring compatibility with the educational framework while fostering inclusivity and engagement.

Currently, the use of video-based supplementary materials has significant implications for teaching and learning. These materials not only align with modern pedagogical approaches but also cater to the digital preferences of 21st-century learners. By integrating multimedia elements, educators can create a more engaging and interactive learning environment, fostering better understanding and retention of complex concepts in examining, defining, differentiating trends from fads, identifying elements and characteristics, and analyzing networks. This approach also supports differentiated instruction, allowing learners with varying abilities to access content at their own pace and level of understanding.

Research Objective Number 2. Identify the content and acceptability level of the supplementary materials in Trends, Networks, and Critical Thinking in the 21st Century.

The content validity of video-enriched supplementary materials in Trends, Networks, and Critical Thinking in the 21st century in terms of Objectives was Highly Valid (3.77). The objectives “relevant to the topics in the 21st Century” and “specific and clearly stated” yielded the highest mean score of 3.87 and were interpreted as Highly Valid. On the other hand, the objectives “time-bound” received the lowest mean score of responses, with 3.60, and were interpreted as Highly Valid. The computed standard deviation of 0.35 indicates a relatively low variability in the responses, suggesting a strong consensus among the evaluators regarding the validity of the objectives.

It implies that the objectives of the video-enriched supplementary materials are well-aligned with educational goals and standards, demonstrating a high level of effectiveness in supporting learning outcomes. The emphasis on objectives being relevant to 21st-century topics and clearly articulated reflects the strong alignment with contemporary educational demands and the clarity needed for guiding learners effectively. The slightly lower evaluation of the "time-bound" aspect suggests room for enhancement in terms of incorporating more specific and measurable time-related goals. Despite this, the high validity rating across all indicators highlights the overall strength and reliability of the materials in addressing the needs of learners and educators within the framework of modern curriculum expectations.

Moreover, Schenk (2024) indicated that learning objectives should be clear, concise, and written using the SMART framework, which stands for Specific, Measurable, Attainable, Relevant, and Time-bound to have an effective and efficient teaching and learning

experience. In addition to this, Navarrete et al. (2023) claimed that though there was no clear what characteristics should have an effective learning medium however it should be aligned with learning objectives and existing course content.

The content validity of the video-enriched supplementary materials in Trends, Networks, and Critical Thinking in the 21st Century in terms of Directions was Highly Valid (3.65). The objective “properly sequenced” yielded the highest mean score of 3.73 and was interpreted as Highly Valid. On the other hand, the aspects “directions being simple and clear” and “easy to follow” received the lowest mean score of responses, with 3.60 and interpreted as Highly Valid. The standard deviation of 0.41 suggests a slightly higher variability in the ratings compared to other components, indicating some differences in the evaluators' perceptions regarding the clarity and sequence of the directions.

It implies that the directions provided in the video-enriched supplementary materials are effective in guiding learners through the learning process, demonstrating a high level of clarity and organization. The emphasis on being "properly sequenced" reflects the materials' ability to present steps and content in a logical and coherent order, facilitating a smoother learning experience. The slightly lower evaluation for the aspects of being "simple and clear" and "easy to follow," while still rated as highly valid, suggests that there might be minor opportunities to refine the language or presentation of directions. This indicates that ensuring absolute simplicity and ease of understanding can further enhance the effectiveness of the supplementary materials, fostering a more accessible and engaging learning environment.

Furthermore, directions in any instructional materials are essential to sustain effective learning. It helps learners understand and execute tasks smoothly, and stay focused. Clear direction promotes independent learning, enhance self-reliance, and foster critical thinking abilities.

This result was similar to Fuhrman (2020), who stated that effective directions should be clear, observable, timed, and concise. With these criteria, it helps students understand what's expected and allows for smooth transitions during lessons.

The content validity of the video-enriched supplementary materials in Trends, Networks, and Critical Thinking in the 21st Century in terms of Topics was Highly Valid (3.72). The materials, as “equipped with background and concepts” and “easily understood by the learners,” received the highest mean score of 3.80 and were interpreted as Highly Valid. On the other hand, “logically presented” received the lowest mean score of 3.60 and was still interpreted as Highly Valid. The computed standard deviation of 0.36 indicates a low level of variability in the responses, demonstrating a consistent agreement among evaluators regarding the appropriateness and clarity of the topics covered.

It implies that the topics covered in the video-enriched supplementary materials are effective and appropriately aligned with learners' needs, as demonstrated by their overall high validity rating. The strong emphasis on being "equipped with background and

concepts" and "easily understood by the learners" highlights the clarity and relevance of the content in supporting the learning process. The slightly lower evaluation of being "logically presented," while still considered highly valid, suggests a minor opportunity for refinement in terms of content organization. This indicates that further adjustments to the logical flow of topics could enhance the overall coherence and accessibility of the materials, ultimately contributing to a more seamless learning experience.

Wong (2020) stated in his study that it was clear that students benefited from using video-based learning, especially in understanding and enriching topics. It made the topic even more interesting, which helped them to comprehend the lesson and improved their learning capacity. Additionally, Kay (as cited in Wong, 2020) discovered that studying through videos improved comprehension and learning motivation of the students, improved grades, and developed better study habits. In short, the use of videos in learning had favorable outcomes.

The importance of items in content validity comes from how they were organized in relation to questions, activities, or affirmations, through the evaluation instrument. Content validity determined how well these items represented the intended content or domain that the instrument was designed to measure.

The content validity of the video-enriched supplementary materials in Trends, Networks, and Critical Thinking in the 21st Century in terms of Practical Exercises was **Highly Valid (3.57)**. The "inconsonance with the objectives", "appropriateness for learners' abilities," and "comprehension enhancement" yielded the highest mean score of **3.60** and were interpreted as **Highly Valid**. On the other hand, the "determination of mastery" and "stimulation of higher-order thinking skills" received the lowest mean score of responses, with **3.53**, and were interpreted as **Highly Valid**. The standard deviation of 0.41 suggests a slightly higher variability in the ratings compared to other components, indicating some differences in the evaluators' perceptions regarding the practical exercises.

It implies that the practical exercises integrated into the video-enriched supplementary materials are effective in supporting learners' development and engagement, as evidenced by their high validity rating overall. The exercises being "in consonance with the objectives," "appropriate for learners' abilities," and promoting "comprehension enhancement" highlight their alignment with educational goals and their adaptability to different learner needs. These qualities ensure that the exercises serve as an essential tool for reinforcing understanding and facilitating meaningful learning experiences. The slightly lower evaluation of their ability to foster "determination of mastery" and "stimulation of higher-order thinking skills," while still considered highly valid, suggests an opportunity to strengthen these aspects. Enhancing these qualities could further enrich the exercises by emphasizing critical thinking and mastery, ultimately elevating their contribution to learners' academic growth and intellectual engagement.

Sewagegn (2020) indicated the importance of exercises in the validity of materials to ensure their effectiveness. And the proper connection of learning objectives and

assessment played a crucial role in the success of student learning, since these two were like a body and soul that cannot be separated from each other.

The content validity of the video-enriched supplementary materials in Trends, Networks, and Critical Thinking in the 21st Century in terms of Clarity was **Highly Valid (3.73)**. The concepts “re-arranged logically and ensuring no duplication” yielded the highest mean score of **3.80** and were interpreted as **Highly Valid**. Whereas, the indicator “information suits learners’ interest” received the lowest mean score of responses, with **3.67**, and was interpreted as **Highly Valid**. The computed standard deviation of 0.37 indicates a low level of variability in the responses, demonstrating a consistent agreement among evaluators regarding the clarity.

It implies that the clarity of the video-enriched supplementary materials is a notable strength, contributing effectively to the learning process. The logical arrangement of concepts and the avoidance of duplication highlight the materials' ability to present information cohesively, ensuring that learners can easily follow the progression of topics without confusion or redundancy. The slightly lower evaluation of the indicator "information suits learners’ interest," while still rated as highly valid, suggests an opportunity to further refine and tailor the content to better align with the preferences and motivations of the learners. This underscores the importance of continuously evaluating and enhancing the relevance of the materials to maintain learner engagement and interest.

The content acceptability of the video-enriched supplementary materials in Trends, Networks, and Critical Thinking in the 21st Century, in terms of Usefulness, was **Very Acceptable (3.73)**. “The concepts in the materials are simple and comprehensible”, and “the material helps the students master the topics at their own pace,” yielded the highest mean score of **3.80** and was interpreted as **Very Acceptable**. On the other hand, the indicator “provides opportunity for development” and “motivates learners to become actively involved in learning activities” received the lowest mean score of responses, with **3.67** and interpreted as **Very Acceptable**. The standard deviation for the general assessment was 0.41, indicating a relatively low variability in the responses, which suggests a consistent perception of the materials' usefulness among the respondents. This level of consistency reinforces the reliability of the evaluation, signifying that most respondents shared a similar view on the video-enriched supplementary materials' effectiveness in facilitating comprehension and self-paced learning.

It implies that the practical utility and benefits of a test are dependent on its usefulness in test acceptability. A test's acceptability is measured by its capacity to give significant and pertinent information on the specific knowledge, skills, talents, or characteristics it seeks to assess. When a test is regarded useful, it means that it accurately analyzes and evaluates the desired abilities or knowledge domains. This relevance makes sure that test results are relevant and applicable to the assessment's intended aims, strengthening overall acceptability and utility in educational or evaluative circumstances. The materials are quite effective at improving logical thinking, learning, and topic mastery. To enhance its impact, it may be helpful to focus on methods that boost learner motivation and provide more opportunities for both personal and educational growth.

According to Tapia (2023), usefulness in tests through utility can provide test acceptability for measuring learners' knowledge. Useful tests were practical in terms of administration, scoring, and interpretation. They should be viable to accomplish given the restrictions of time, resources, and the desired testing environment.

The content acceptability of the video-enriched supplementary materials in Trends, Networks, and Critical Thinking in the 21st Century, in terms of Presentation, was **Very Acceptable (3.80)**. "The topics are presented in logical and sequential order," yielded the highest mean score of **3.87** and was interpreted as **Very Acceptable**. On the other hand, the indicator "presentation of each lesson is attractive and interesting" received the lowest mean score of responses, with **3.73**, and was interpreted as **Very Acceptable**. The standard deviation was 0.34, indicating a relatively low variability in the responses. This suggests a consistent perception of the materials' presentation among the respondents, reinforcing the reliability of the evaluation.

It implies that the presentation of video-enriched supplementary materials in Trends, Networks, and Critical Thinking in the 21st Century is presented in logical and sequential order and fits the learners' needs. It also denotes that the video-enriched supplementary materials met the standards. The materials are effective in delivering content in a structured and engaging manner that significantly contributes to fostering critical thinking and understanding of trends and networks in the modern era.

Echallas (2023) mentioned that the content should be effectively presented, formatted, and arranged knowledge can be exciting and enjoyable to learners, making them more engaged in learning about diverse topics. The content, structure, presentation, and arrangement, as well as the quality and timeliness of the information, are all very much appreciated.

The content acceptability of the video-enriched supplementary materials in Trends, Networks, and Critical Thinking in the 21st Century in terms of Suitability was **Very Acceptable (3.67)**. "The language of the program is within the vocabulary range of learners" yielded the highest mean score of **3.73** and was interpreted as **Very Acceptable**. On the other hand, the indicator "activities consider the varying attitudes and capabilities" received the lowest mean score of responses, with **3.60**, and was interpreted as **Very Acceptable**. The standard deviation for the general assessment of Suitability was 0.43, indicating a relatively consistent perception among respondents regarding the appropriateness of the materials. This suggests that most responses were closely clustered around the mean scores, reinforcing the reliability of the evaluation.

It implies that the suitability of video-enriched supplementary materials is aligned with the specific characteristics and specifications of the individuals or situations are intended. It also denotes that the video-enriched supplementary materials met the standards. The materials are effective in providing suitable content for learners that significantly contributes to fostering critical thinking and understanding of trends and networks in the modern era.

Onur et al. (2023) emphasized that appropriateness plays a crucial role in enhancing test acceptability, underscoring the importance of ensuring that a test aligns with the specific needs and characteristics of its intended population. The adequacy of a test is not merely a technical concern but a fundamental aspect of its overall credibility and effectiveness. A well-designed test, meticulously structured to accommodate the diverse traits, goals, and expectations of its target users, fosters confidence in its results. By considering factors such as cognitive abilities, cultural background, language proficiency, and learning styles, test developers can create assessments that are more inclusive and representative. This inclusivity strengthens the reliability of the test, ensuring that it provides valid measurements while promoting fairness and accessibility.

Research objective Number 3: Determine the pretest and posttest scores of the Grade 12 Students in Trends, Networks, and Critical Thinking in the 21st Century.

The students **Did not meet Expectations (74.71)**. There were 4 students, or 11.43% were Very Satisfactory, 5 students, or 14.29% were Satisfactory, 8 students, or 22.86% were Fairly Satisfactory, and 18 students, or 51.43 %, who Did not Meet Expectations. The Standard Deviation was 7.21, indicating a moderate level of variability in the students' performance. This suggests that while the majority of students fell into the "Did Not Meet Expectations" category, there was still some dispersion among the different performance levels.

It implies that, prior to the implementation of the video-enriched supplementary materials, the majority of students faced challenges in meeting the expected performance standards for the subject. The distribution of varying levels of performance highlights the need for innovative instructional strategies to address gaps in understanding and engagement effectively. The significant proportion of students who struggled suggests that traditional teaching methods may not have sufficiently accommodated diverse learning needs or maintained the interest of learners. This underscores the importance of integrating supplementary materials, such as video-based tools, to provide additional support and improve the overall learning experience.

According to Vavasseur et al. (2020), poor pretest scores indicated that there was a need for improvement in topic delivery so that students might perform well in the subject. Low pretest scores can indicate an opportunity for improvement. This information was useful since it helped instructors discover knowledge gaps that needed to be filled.

The students were **Very Satisfactory (86.63)**. There were 16 students, or 45.71% of the 35 total number of students have performed Outstanding in the post-test, 10 or 28.57% were able to performed Very Satisfactory, while 4 or 11.43% of the students have performed Satisfactory. Moreover, 14.29% or 5 students did not meet expectations. The standard deviation was 7.42, indicating a moderate level of variability in students' post-test performance. This suggests that the scores were fairly consistent, with the majority of students clustering around the higher performance levels.

This simply means that the majority of the students performed well in the post-test after the execution of developed video-enriched supplementary materials in Grade 12

HUMSS. The said supplementary materials contribute greatly on students' performance. Hence, there was a percentage of learners who did not meet the required expectation.

According to Mondragon et al. (2023), supplemental learning materials will improve students' performance, as demonstrated by the post-test for the digital intervention material. Several elements influenced the overall learning experience, including student involvement, instructional design, and evaluation systems. When used carefully and effectively, video-enriched supplementary materials can enhance the learning experience and potentially result in higher grades.

There was a significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores of the students with a t value of -64.091 (SD=5.79, $x = -27.12$) and the probability value is .000, which was less than the level of significance at .05, thus the null hypothesis was rejected.

It implies that the implementation of the video-enriched supplementary materials has a meaningful and measurable effect on the students' performance in the subject *Trends, Networks, and Critical Thinking in the 21st Century*. The rejection of the null hypothesis indicates that the improvement in scores from pretest to posttest is not due to chance, but rather a result of the intervention. This suggests that the materials are successful in enhancing the students' learning experience, contributing to their better understanding and mastery of the subject. It emphasizes the effectiveness of integrating innovative teaching strategies to address learning gaps and support academic achievement.

Mercado (2022) found out that students who were exposed to video clip presentations performed better than those who were taught using traditional methods, as shown in the post-test results comparing the performance of students who viewed video clips with those who did not. Furthermore, (Umayam, 2024) quote that "video is also proving to have solid results when it comes to learning outcomes, from higher test scores to increased engagement with learning materials to increase comprehension". It is noticeable the changes in approach in today's learners.

Conclusions

The development and validation of video-enriched supplementary materials in TRENDS, NETWORKS, AND CRITICAL THINKING IN THE 21st CENTURY for Grade 12 Senior High School Students successfully addressed the educational challenges faced by Grade 12 learners in University of Perpetual Help System DALTA - Calamba Campus, particularly their low performance in Trends. Anchored on the principles of Behavioral Learning Theory, Cognitive Load Theory, and Law of Effect and Exercise Theory the module was systematically crafted using the ADDIE model to meet the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) outlined by the Department of Education.

In terms of **content validity**, the module received a perfect Content Validity Index (CVI) of 1.00 and was rated Highly Valid across all indicators: objectives, directions, topics, practical exercises, and clarity. Additionally, expert Social Studies teachers rated its **acceptability** as Very Acceptable based on usefulness, presentation, and suitability.

This shows the video-enriched was relevance and practical use in real classroom settings

The **educational impact** of the video-enriched was evident in the significant improvement in students' academic performance. The pretest average of 74.71 (Did Not Meet Expectations) rose to a posttest average of 86.63 (Very Satisfactory). A paired t-test confirmed a statistically significant difference ($t = -64.091$, $p < .000$). This demonstrated the video-enriched supplementary materials' effectiveness in improving comprehension and retention through clear, engaging, and focused learning segments.

The **assessment strategies** included in the video-enriched supplementary materials—pretest and posttest evaluations, performance tasks, and reflective activities—validated its success in addressing learners' short attention spans and in improving foundational knowledge in Trends, Networks and Critical Thinking in the 21st Century. These assessments matched well with the IDEA (Introduction, Development, Engagement, Assimilation) model, enabling a seamless learning process.

Finally, **feedback from teachers and stakeholders** was overwhelmingly positive. Teachers recognized the video-enriched supplementary materials potential to enhance the delivery of education, particularly in a subject like Trends, Networks, and Critical Thinking in the 21st Century that often struggled with innovation. Stakeholders, including school administrators and parents, recognized its usefulness, modified it for blended and modular learning, and observed that it was in line with students' digital habits.

Overall, the study demonstrated that teaching with video-enriched supplemental materials offered a creative and successful means of imparting critical thinking, networks, and trends skills in the twenty-first century. The resources served as a remedy for contemporary educational issues such student disengagement, content overload, and digital distractions in addition to being a tool for delivering content.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions drawn, the following recommendations are proposed:

For Teachers and Instructional Designers

Educators are encouraged to integrate the video-enriched supplementary materials in Social Studies and other subjects. By employing the I.D.E.A. format for modular lessons, educators can create a structured yet flexible learning environment that caters to diverse learning styles.

For School Administrators and Curriculum Planners

Schools and curriculum developers are advised to consider the integration of video-enriched supplementary materials into their regular instructional plans, particularly for subjects that are content-heavy or commonly neglected in modular learning. Implementing video-enriched supplementary materials can aid in the equitable and effective delivery of important competences.

For the Department of Education (DepEd)

The DepEd may consider the implementation and integration of video-enriched supplementary resources across major learning areas in basic education. This aligns with the goals of the Basic Education Development Plan (BEDP) 2030 and addresses learner diversity and adaptability.

For Future Researchers

Future research could build on this work by exploring the long-term impacts of video-enriched materials on knowledge retention, their applicability to different subjects and grade levels, and their effect on student motivation. Qualitative research on learner experiences and input could help improve the design of future modules.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study observed ethical guidelines established by the Laguna College of Business and Arts Thesis Writing Manual and the Data Privacy Act of 2012. Respondents gave informed consent, which ensured voluntary participation without pressure. All data were encrypted to ensure privacy and confidentiality. Finally, the utility of Canva platforms and Powtoon has been useful and addressed in this research.

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